

Munir's Socio-Eco-Environmental Approach to Environmental Education for Communities, Living

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Munir's socio-eco-environmental approach to environmental education is a conceptual model for communities, living under unprecedented emergencies. According to Munir, decision-making regarding developing environmental literacy programs that support sustainable educational practice should begin with a consideration of socio-economic elements. Initially, a scoping review can help understand how the socio, cultural, and political geography of ABC country shape the ways people interact with each other and their environments. It must be followed by knowing socio-psychological trauma and healing mechanisms through the lens of local people of varied age groups- examining the mental health challenges faced by people during the environmental catastrophe, as well as the resources available to support their well-being and how they contribute to their well-being. A good number of strategies may help, for example, ethnography, interviews, drawing, and photovoice. Next, the state of environmental literacy must be confirmed via desk review followed by behavioral mapping, i.e., awareness, skills, and attitudes, related to environmental issues and ecological identity exploration. Assessing existing knowledge, skills, and attitudes can aid in comprehending the actual opportunities and gaps in delivering an environmental literacy course; and delving into the intricacies of one's relationship with the environment can provide valuable insight into how it influences and molds one's core values, convictions, and actions that may also help in crafting contextual course. To develop a comprehensive course on environmental literacy, a design thinking approach that integrates empathy mapping and ethnographic methods should be employed to identify socio-cultural, educational, and environmental challenges from the perspective of the actual participants who will benefit from the course. Additionally, a shift away from anthropocentrism towards ecocentrism is necessary to draft an effective and impactful course.